

**FINE ACTIVITIES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION
AS A DEPARTMENT OF INTEGRATIVE CONTENT**

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Abstract: In this article, the role of educators in the formation of children's aesthetic abilities through the use of visual aids in preschool education is of particular importance, as well as deep knowledge and high skills, regular self-study, continuous improvement of their scientific and theoretical level, reliance on best practices Recognizing the importance of mainly Visual activity is the largest section that acquires integrative content and highlights the recommendations that are implemented in a logical and didactic connection with other types of activities.

Key words: Integrative content, logic, didactic, fine arts, color imagery, graphics, sculpture, decorative arts, pupil, preschool, education, comprehension, knowledge, taste, decorative, application, action games, social, independence, talent

INTRODUCTION

It is known that the role of the educator in the formation of children's aesthetic abilities through visual activities in preschool educational institutions is invaluable. He must have deep knowledge and high qualifications, for this he must work on himself regularly, constantly raise his scientific-theoretical level, rely on advanced experience.

It should be noted that the visual activity is the largest part of the integrative content and is carried out in a logical and didactic connection with other types of activity. This factor means that the content and methodology of visual activities need to be improved in line with other types of activities.

In fact, in preschool education, children are mainly engaged in practical work in the field of visual arts, storytelling with works of art; and in school, the types of fine arts become more deeply acquainted with works of color painting, graphics, sculpture, and decorative art. In the preschool organization, the activities of visual arts are diverse: drawing, clay, application, construction. Great attention is paid to all the lessons presented in the preschool organization. The successful solution of educational problems in the primary grades is integrated with the lessons of descriptive activities in preschool education. In group art activities, children learn to control their character and hand power with the free use of pencils and brushes. This, in turn, develops the ability to move the hand in a light, free plane in children. In the process of drawing objects of different shapes, sizes, proportions, children learn to move in accordance with the size of the object, the need to maintain direction, depending on the nature of the work of the object. In pre-school educational activities, students learn to use materials in an orderly manner, to keep them clean, to plan only the necessary materials and ways to use them. These exercises develop attention and visual memory in children.

In the preparatory group of preschool education organizations, the requirements for drawing or depiction will increase depending on the nature, and these requirements will approach the demand of the school. Demonstrating the sequence of work in nature-based imaging is done only at the initial stage of preparation and study in a large group of children. Children try to analyze nature by drawing the whole general form on sketch paper, comparing the picture to nature, correcting mistakes and shortcomings, and likening it to nature. Finding or seeing geometric shapes in visual activities, naming them in terms of width, size, length, height, and spatial location of parts relative to each other will help children to master elementary

mathematical concepts in first grade. Building from building materials in construction classes builds visual acuity in children and helps children to master or master technical lessons in school. Thus, in visual arts classes, children's artistic taste and creative abilities are developed, and through this they are prepared for school. Because children are inextricably linked with objects, get acquainted with their unique qualities, shape, color, size, identify their differences, similarities, which allows children to develop sensory, visual, figurative thinking.

Visual activities educate children morally. In their work, children reflect the events that take place in their lives, in society, they are happy and excited. In the process of visual activity, children are taught the qualities of the will - to finish the work, to set goals and strive to achieve them, to overcome difficulties, to help their peers. Qualities such as helping each other, working together in the process of creating teamwork; in the process of evaluating work, they develop ethical qualities such as a realistic attitude of their peers towards work, correct evaluation, satisfaction with their work and the work of their peers.

Pupils - children attending preschool educational institutions; orphanages, children in specialized boarding schools, and adolescents in out-of-school institutions. Preschool is an educational institution that implements various programs of preschool education. Education is a product of teaching, which is the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students in the learning process. Knowledge, on the other hand, is the result of knowing the existence of being tested in practice and logically confirmed.

CONCLUSION

So, the conclusion is that the role of the educator in teaching visual activities in preschool education is great, teaching them to use the material in order, to keep it clean, to plan only the necessary materials and ways to use them. These lessons develop children's attention and visual memory. Visual activity is carried out in a logical and didactic connection with other types of activities as the largest section,

which acquires integrative content. This means that the content and methodology of visual activities need to be improved in line with other activities.

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